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Taxonomic key for identifying the 22 species in the genus Oryza

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The IRGC is receiving more and more requests for seeds of

wild species of Oryza, from both rice scientists and biotech workers using rice as an experimental material. Recent revisions in the taxonomy and nomenclature of the 20 wild species and 2 cultigens (cultivated species) in the genus (Chang, 1985) necessitate a revised taxonomic key to identify newly collected materials or to reevaluate

previous identification.

A working key prepared earlier (Chang, 1976) has been revised and updated to assist biologists using the wild species as novel sources of resistance to diseases and insects and tolerance for eco-edaphic stresses (see Chang, 1988; Chang & Vaughan, 1989).

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A working key to the valid species of *Oryza* (modified after Roschevitz, 1931; Chatterjee, 1948; Tateoka, 1963; Bardenas and Chang, 1966; Tateoka, 1965; Sharma and Shastri, 1965; Ng et al., 1981).

- A-1 Sterile lemmas present
- B-1 Sterile lemmas linear or linear lanceolate
- C-1 Ligule of lower leaves 14-45 mm long, tips acute
- D-1 Annual; leaf blades narrow; no rhizomes; spikelets persistent, 3-14 mm long, 2-5 mm wide; Asian origin; cultivated; diploid *sativa*
- D-2 Annual; semi-erect to decumbent growth; without rhizomes; basal internodes spongy; spikelets oblong and deciduous; short anthers; Asian origin; diploid *nivara*
- D-3 Annual, some perennial; erect to semi-erect growth; without rhizomes; tightly adpressed short secondary rachises resulting in more compact panicle; stiff, erect, ascending panicle branches; Australian origin; diploid *meridionalis*
- E-1 Perennial; erect habit; branched, spreading rhizomes; long anthers fill entire spikelet; elliptic pollen; African origin; diploid *longistaminata*
- E-2 Perennial; prostrate or floating habit; weak rhizomes; long anthers; adventitious roots and extravaginal branching at higher nodes; long internodes; lax panicles; long, slender, deciduous spikelets; Asian origin; diploid *rufipogon*
- E-3 Perennial; semi-erect habit; stoloniferous culms; long awns and long spikelets; American origin; diploid *glumaepatula*
- C-2 Ligule of lower leaves shorter than 6 mm, tip round or truncate
- D-4 Sterile lemmas almost equal in length and similar in structure to lemma and palea; ligule with a fringe of hairs at the apex; leaves broad; American origin; perennial; tetraploid *grandiglumis*
- D-5 Sterile lemmas considerably shorter than the lemma and palea
- E-4 Annual; plants erect; leaves glabrous to slightly scabrid; panicles more or less compact; lemma and palea perfectly or almost perfectly glabrous; sometimes hispid; spikelets usually awnless or short-awned; main panicle axis without secondary or tertiary branches; spikelet length between 7-9 mm; spikelet width 2.9-3.6 mm; tip of sterile lemmas acute; African origin; cultivated; diploid *glaberrima*
- E-5 Annual; plants erect to spreading; panicles open, main axis with secondary or rarely tertiary branches; lemma and palea hispid; spikelets 7.8-11.0 mm long, 2.8-3.4 mm wide, always awned (10 cm or longer); awns bristled; sterile lemmas 2.1-5.0 mm long, acuminate at tip; African origin; diploid *barthii*^a
- E-6 Perennial; main axis of panicle slightly woolly pubescent at the base of primary branches, the rest smooth and glabrous; axis increasingly hispid-scabrid toward the tip; awns less than 5 cm long; sterile lemmas linear or linear lanceolate; rhizomatous; Australian origin; diploid *australiensis*
- E-7 Ligule with a fringe of hairs at the apex
- F-1 Perennial; plant not rhizomatous; leaves broad
- G-1 Width of leaves less than 5 cm; spikelets less than 7 mm long; American origin; tetraploid *latifolia*
- G-2 Width of leaves more than 5 cm; spikelets more than 7 mm long; American origin; tetraploid *alta*
- E-8 Ligule without fringe of hairs at the apex; leaves less than 2 cm broad
- F-2 Width of spikelets less than 2 mm
- G-3 Panicle branches not spreading; length of spikelets 4.5-6.0 mm, width 1.5-2.0 mm; culm base slender, hard and not spongy; ligule less than 3.5 mm, never split, hard, flexuous with fine bristles; sterile lemmas acuminate and narrowly triangular; African origin; perennial; diploid *eichingeri*
- G-4 Length of spikelets 3.7-4.7 mm; width usually less than 2 mm; panicle small with spreading branches; awned (2 cm or less) or awnless; Asian origin; perennial; tetraploid *minuta*
- F-3 Width of spikelet more than 2 mm
- G-5 Length of spikelets more than 5 mm; width 2.0-2.5 mm; culm base soft and spongy; ligule longer than 3.0 mm, soft, and split when dried; straight or flexuous with rigid bristles; panicle loose with spreading branches; sterile lemmas acute and triangular; African origin; perennial; tetraploid *punctata*
- E-9 Ligule glabrous or hairy; length of spikelets less than 5 mm, width almost always more than 2 mm; awns often shorter than 2 cm, or awnless; occasionally rhizomatous; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *officinalis*
- A-2 Sterile lemmas subulate or setaceous
- B-2 Surface of sterile lemmas and palea granulate; sterile lemmas minute, long, tapered from base; usually awnless
- C-3 Spikelets oblong to elliptic oblong, shorter than 7 mm; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *granulata*
- C-4 Spikelets narrowly oblong to lanceolate, longer than 7 mm; Asian origin; perennial; diploid *meyeriana*
- B-3 Surface of lemma and palea not granulate; awned; spikelets 8-17 mm long
- C-5 Lemma ciliate along keel, without wing; leaves herbaceous
- D-6 Awns 6-15 mm long; sterile lemmas shorter than lemma; Asian origin; perennial; tetraploid *ridleyi*
- D-7 Awns 16-36 mm long; sterile lemmas as long as or longer than lemma; New Guinean origin; perennial; tetraploid *longiglumis*
- B-4 Surface of lemma almost smooth with fine longitudinally dotted stippled surface
- C-6 Spikelets linear, 1-2 mm wide; awns 6-17 mm long; sterile lemmas always much shorter than lemma; African origin; annual; diploid *brachyantha*
- A-3 Spikelets 1.5-1.75 mm long; nodes hairy; New Guinean origin *schlechteri*

NOTES:

- Excluded from the key are taxa of doubtful validity or names of uncertain application: *O. abromeitiana*, *O. collina*, *O. fatua*, *O. malampuzhaensis*, *O. perennis*, *O. perennis* subsp. *cubensis*, *O. schweinfurthiana*, *O. stapfii*, *O. ubanghensis*, and *O. indandamanica*.
- Removed from the genus *Oryza* are taxa formerly known as '*O. angustifolia*', '*O. perrieri*', and '*O. tisseranti*' - to the genus *Leersia*; '*O. coarctata*' (renamed as *Porteresia coarctata*); and '*O. subulata*' (to the genus *Rhynchoriza*).
- For specimens of uncertain morphological identity, a determination of somatic chromosome numbers from young root-tips will be helpful in certain cases.
- Annual and perennial growth habits are rather difficult to distinguish when the plants are grown under tropical conditions; the term "annual" refers to a primary seed-propagated form while "perennial" refers to a taxon adapted to vegetative propagation by underground plant parts.

^aFormerly known as *O. breviligulata*, includes the weed race *O. stapfii*.